

The VIASM-HANU BMF Class Paper Solved Kingfisher's Food Worry

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April 20, 2024

Following the joint efforts by participants in the VIASM-HANU BMF Class, part of the Conference on Innovations of Mathematics Teaching in Social Sciences co-organized by the Vietnam Institute for Advanced Study in Mathematics (VIASM) and Hanoi University (HANU) in early November 2023, a joint manuscript was submitted to the [VMOST Journal of Social Sciences and Humanities](#).

The peer review process was successfully completed in February, and the paper was officially published today (see the screenshot below).

The screenshot displays the article page for the journal. At the top, there is a navigation bar with links for SECTIONS, ABOUT, PEER-REVIEW PROCESS, ONLINE JOURNAL SYSTEM, CURRENT PUBLICATIONS, ARCHIVES, and ACCEPTED ARTICLES. The article title is "Effects of water scarcity awareness and climate change belief on recycled water usage willingness: Evidence from New Mexico, United States". Below the title, a list of authors is provided: Minh-Hoang Nguyen*, Duc Manh Doan, Hanh Kim Dong, Van Thi Nguyen, Hanh Hong Dao, Duy Duc Trinh, Nhai Thi Nguyen, Kim Nguyet Kieu, Nhung Quynh Thi Le, Ha Thu Thi Hoang, Van Ngoc Thi Dam, Dung Hoang Do, Thu Thi Vu, Tu That Ton, Nhi Yen Nguyen, Nhi Van Nguyen, Thu Tai Le, Hoa Tuan Pham, and Binh Thi Khuat. The journal cover is shown, featuring the title "VMOST Journal of Social Sciences and Humanities" and the issue information "APRIL 2024 - VOLUME 06 NUMBER 1". A PDF icon is visible below the cover. On the right side, there are logos for iThenticate (Professional Plagiarism Prevention), Crossref, and Google Scholar. The page also indicates that all submissions are screened by iThenticate and that the journal is a member of Crossref. The publication date is listed as 2024-04-20, with a note that the article was received on 6 November 2023, revised on 3 January 2024, and accepted on 21 February 2024.

Illustration: The VIASM-HANU BMF Class article appears in VMOST JOSSH [1]

The SM3D community wholeheartedly congratulates all the article's authors on their publishing event. The [BMF analytics](#) [2] had been used efficiently and effectively during the preparatory process leading to the desired outcome.

Since the paper deals with the problem of water scarcity and climate change, [Mr. Kingfisher](#) can now be assured that more researchers have been spending time to sort out his long-standing worry about his fishing territory, de facto the food security problem [3].

References

[1] Nguyen MH, Doan DM, Dong HK, ... Do VC. (2024). Effects of water scarcity awareness and climate change belief on recycled water usage willingness: Evidence from New Mexico, United States. *V MOST Journal of Social Sciences and Humanities*, 66(1), 62-75. [https://doi.org/10.31276/VMOSTJOSSH.66\(1\).62-75](https://doi.org/10.31276/VMOSTJOSSH.66(1).62-75)

[2] Vuong QH, Nguyen MH, La VP. (Eds.)(2022). *The mindsponge and BMF analytics for innovative thinking in social sciences and humanities*. Walter de Gruyter GmbH. <https://www.amazon.com/dp/BOC4ZK3M74>

[3] Vuong QH. (2022). *The Kingfisher Story Collection*. <https://www.amazon.com/dp/BOBG2NNHY6>

